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SoildiverAgro

Soil biodiversity enhancement in European agroecosystems to promote their stability and resilience by external inputs reduction and crop performance increase

D4.1- REPORT ON IMPLEMENTATION AND OPTIMIZATION OF QMEC HT-QPCR CHIP FOR CHARACTERIZATION OF MICROBIAL FUNCTIONAL DIVERSITY

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D4.1. REPORT ON IMPLEMENTATION AND OPTIMIZATION OF QMEC HT-QPCR CHIP FOR CHARACTERIZATION OF MICROBIAL FUNCTIONAL DIVERSITY

Summary

Microbial communities in soil ecosystems play pivotal roles in nutrient cycling, organic matter decomposition, and soil structure regulation. Single-gene quantitative PCR (qPCR) has constraints in scalability and depth of functional gene characterization, whereas metagenomics remains costly and labor intensive for functional diversity surveys. The Quantitative Microbial Ecology Chip (QMEC) HT-qPCR chip emerges as a high-throughput tool for simultaneously quantifying functional genes in soil ecosystems, promising standardized, high-throughput assessment, while at the same time offering high sample throughput and relatively economical analysis. This study evaluated the recently developed QMEC chip, by analyzing 31 datasets (701 soil samples) for primer efficiency, specificity, and amplification. Results identify primer pairs exhibiting robustness (>50% efficiency) and highlight challenges with specific genes, indicating rarity or specificity issues. Additionally, an updated ureC primer pair is validated through PCR and amplicon sequencing, demonstrating improved detection of ureolytic bacterial communities. Moreover, the QMEC chip's applicability for detecting changes following agrochemical inputs was assessed in a controlled microcosm experiment with different amendments of glyphosate/Roundup and artificial root exudates in soil. The microbial community and functionality responses were pronounced in ARE-amended soils, showcasing the effectiveness of the QMEC chip in assessing functional diversity alterations. Overall, this study validated the QMEC chip's utility for comprehensive soil functional diversity studies, showcasing its potential for surveying functional diversity of soil prokaryotic communities at the continental scale as needed by the SoildiverAgro consortium (WP5).

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1 Introduction

Within the intricate matrix of soil ecosystems, microbial communities are responsible for functions crucial for ecosystem health and productivity (Fierer, 2017). These microorganisms, encompassing a diverse array of bacteria, fungi, and archaea, drive fundamental processes such as nutrient cycling, organic matter decomposition, and the regulation of soil structure (Delgado-Baquerizo *et al.*, 2018). Understanding the functional diversity and dynamics of these microbial communities is pivotal for unraveling ecosystem processes and devising strategies for sustainable land management and environmental stewardship (Osburn *et al.*, 2023).

The comprehensive evaluation of microbial functional diversity within soil ecosystems encounters multifaceted challenges. Traditional methodologies such as quantitative PCR (qPCR), have historically relied on manual, labor-intensive processes. The intricacies involved in primer design, optimization, and the subsequent quantification of functional genes associated with microbial communities limit the scalability and throughput of these analyses. This limitation constrains the breadth and depth of functional gene characterization and impedes a holistic understanding of microbial functional potential within diverse soil environments.

The Quantitative Microbial Ecology Chip (QMEC) HT-qPCR chip constitutes a promising new technology that may help overcome the constraints encountered in conventional methodologies (Zheng *et al.*, 2018). The technology presents a high-throughput platform for simultaneous quantification of 71 microbial functional genes involved in biogeochemical cycling of C, N, P, and S in soil ecosystems (Zheng *et al.*, 2018). Leveraging an array of primer pairs targeting key functional genes, the QMEC chip promises high throughput, reduced manual labor, and a standardized methodology for characterizing microbial functional potential relative to competing functional gene quantification platforms such as conventional single-gene qPCR, metagenomics, or cultivation-based approaches. Hence, the QMEC chip holds promise in expediting the analysis of diverse functional genes across microbial communities within soil ecosystems. Its potential to streamline and broaden functional gene assessment provides an avenue for a more comprehensive understanding of microbial functional diversity. However, the successful deployment of the QMEC chip necessitates attention to inherent limitations (Bustin *et al.*, 2009). Rigorous validation of primer pairs integrated into the chip is paramount, requiring specificity checks and assessment of amplification efficiency. Furthermore, optimizing primer pairs to accommodate the nuances of soil systems and the diverse environmental conditions prevalent within different ecosystems remains an ongoing challenge.

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This report serves as a comprehensive exploration into the implementation and optimization of the QMEC HT-qPCR chip for characterizing microbial functional diversity within soil ecosystems. To achieve this we: (i) Evaluated each primer pair of the QMEC chip by analyzing technical parameters (Cycle threshold (CT) values, amplification efficiency, and melting curves) of 31 previous QMEC datasets (701 soil samples), (ii) Modified existing primer pairs to optimize accurate gene detection and (iii) Utilized the QMEC chip in a controlled microcosm experiment to assess its applicability at evaluating changes in functional diversity following external inputs (agrochemicals).

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Evaluation of QMEC chip using meta-analysis

To comprehensively evaluate the efficiency and accuracy of QMEC chip, threshold cycle (CT) values, amplification efficiency measures, and melting curves from 31 previous QMEC chip datasets were downloaded and analyzed. The datasets encompassed 701 samples collected from various regions, including China, Australia, and Europe, categorized across different soil types including forest soil, agricultural soils, and permafrost soil. All datasets had been analyzed using the full primer set of the QMEC chip (Table A1) and all datasets were generated using the recommended concentration of DNA (20 to 30 ng/ul). The sample overview is detailed in Table 1.

Table 1 Detailed information of the samples used for the meta-analysis

Country/Region	Soil Type	Number of collected samples
China	Forest soil	120
	Agricultural soil	227
	Permafrost soil	0
Australia	Forest soil	108
	Agricultural soil	0
	Permafrost soil	0
Europe	Forest soil	0
	Agricultural soil	177
	Permafrost soil	69
Total		701

CT-value analysis: The Ct value represents the PCR cycle number where fluorescence significantly surpasses a predetermined threshold. In regards to the QMEC chip, only Ct values above 0 and below 31 were considered successful amplifications (Su *et al.*, 2021). Ct values above the 31 threshold indicate that the functional gene can be detected, but the relative abundance is too low to use for gene quantification. In this report, Ct value analysis are used to assess the frequency of successful amplification of each primer pair across the 31 datasets. Primer pairs with low level of successful amplification may indicate problems with the primer pair and therefore may need optimization, or it could mean that the targeted genes are non-ideal functional biomarkers in soil.

Melting curve analysis: Melting curve analysis is pivotal for ensuring specificity and accuracy in qPCR. It confirms the amplification of the intended target DNA by detecting distinct melting peaks. A single peak signifies specific amplification, while multiple peaks indicate potential non-specific amplification or contamination. This analysis serves as a quality check, aids in optimizing PCR conditions, and troubleshoots unexpected results, ensuring reliable experimental outcomes. In this report, melting curve analysis was used to validate the specificity and accuracy of the QMEC primer pairs.

PCR Amplification efficiency: Assessing amplification efficiency in qPCR is crucial for gauging the accuracy of DNA amplification. It measures how effectively the target DNA is replicated during the PCR process. In this report, a efficiency value between 1.8 and 2.1 reflects optimal amplification, while values lower than 1.8 may indicate suboptimal performance. Evaluating amplification efficiency ensures the reliability and precision of the qPCR results, aiding in data interpretation and experimental accuracy. Table 2 details the parameters for the meta-analysis.

Table 2 Description of parameters used for evaluation in the meta-analysis

Parameters	Group	Description
Ct Value	Ct=0	The functional gene cannot be detected in QMEC chip system
	0<Ct<31	The functional gene can be well amplified and quantified in QMEC chip system
	Ct>31	The functional gene can be detected, but the relative abundance is too low to use for downstream analysis
Melting Curve	Multiple melting peaks	The functional gene may have no-specific amplification and the results should be cautiously processed
	One peak	The result is reliable in QMEC thermal cycler
Amplification efficiency	Efficiency<1.8	Low amplification efficiency in QMEC reaction system
	1.8<Efficiency<2.1	Normal amplification efficiency in QMEC reaction system

2.1 Specificity and Coverage of new UreC primer pair

The original primer pair targeting the *ureC* gene showed low detectability and amplification efficiency in the initial QMEC validation (see results of meta study). The primer pair was therefore changed based on previous literature (Reed, 2001) in an attempt to improve detection of the *UreC* gene (see Table 3).

Table 3. Original and new primers for the UreC gene.

Original primers	New primers
UreC-F 5'-AAGMTSCACGAGGACTGGGG-3'	UreC-F 5'- TGGGCCTTAAAATHCAYGARGAYTGGG-3'
ureC-R (5'-AGRTGGTGGCASACCATTSAGCAT-3')	UreC-R (5'-GGTGGTGGCACACCATNANCATRTC-3')

The specificity and coverage of the new primer pair were subsequently evaluated using PCR and amplicon sequencing. In brief, DNA extracts from three soils were used for PCR amplification. The PCR reaction was performed in 50- μ L reactions containing 25 μ L of Premix Ex Taq (TaKaRa, Dalian), 0.2 μ mol L⁻¹ of each primer, 1 ng μ L⁻¹ of DNA template and 0.1 mg mL⁻¹ bovine serum albumin. The samples were amplified with an initial denaturation at 95°C for 5 min and 35 cycles of denaturation at 95°C for 30 s, annealing at 58°C for 30 s, and extension at 72°C for 30 s, followed by a final extension at 72°C for 5 min. The PCR products were subsequently purified (Universal DNA purification kit, TIANGEN, Beijing), quantified (QuantiFluor dsDNA kit, Promega), pooled at equal molar concentrations and sequenced using an Illumina Hiseq2500 platform (Novogen, Tianjin). The raw reads were filtered and aligned with bacterial sequences in the Reference Sequence (RefSeq) database (<ftp://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/refseq/release>) using Local Blast 2.2.27+ (<ftp://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/blast/executables/blast+/2.2.27/>). The e-value of the alignments was set at 10⁻⁵, and the highest score was accepted. The aligned result with hypothetical protein was excluded. The **coverage** was calculated based on proportion of DNA sequences classified at specific level. The primer specificity (%) was the proportion of sequence counts which was aligned with RefSeq database ($\text{Count}_{\text{align}}$) to total filtered sequence counts ($\text{Count}_{\text{total}}$) (equation 1).

$$\text{Specificity} = \text{Count}_{\text{align}} / \text{Count}_{\text{total}} \quad (1)$$

2.1 Implementation of the updated QMEC chip in a soil microcosm experiment

Experimental setup: The applicability of the updated QMEC chip was tested in a controlled soil microcosm setup, with the aim of investigating if the QMEC chip can be used to detect the impacts of agrochemicals (Glyphosate) on microbial functionality. Soil for the microcosms was collected from an experimental agriculture field site (Field no. 26), located at Højbakkegård, University of Copenhagen, Taastrup, Denmark. The detailed physicochemical properties of the field soil are described in previous literature (Fernández-Calviño *et al.*, 2017). The field had no history of herbicide application. Soil was sampled in May 2020 from the depth of 0-20 cm according to the OECD 217 guideline (OECD, 2000) and was stored at 4 °C until analysis (1 week). Prior to the experiment, the soil was air-dried for 24 h at 22 °C and then sieved through a 2 mm sieve. Soil microcosms were prepared in 50 mL falcon tube containing 5 g of soil. Two series of microcosms were set up using the air-dried soil; one series was amended with Artificial root exudate (ARE), to imitate hotspot soil (Brandt *et al.*, 2009), at the beginning of the experiment, while the other series only received Milli Q water. Subsequently, each series of microcosms was spiked with increasing glyphosate or Roundup concentrations. The final concentrations of glyphosate (CAS no. 1071-83-6) and Roundup (active ingredient: 360 g/L glyphosate, Monsanto Crop Sciences Danmark A/S) in the microcosms were 1, 10, and 100 µg/g dry soil, reflecting environmentally relevant glyphosate concentrations in soil (Busse *et al.*, 2001). Milli Q water was sprayed into the microcosm soil resulting in soil moisture of 7% to ensure homogeneous distribution of glyphosate (Roundup) and ARE through manual mixing. Microcosms were incubated in the dark at 20±2 °C for 42 days. At day 42 of incubation, samples were collected for DNA extraction (see details below).

DNA extraction: A subsample of each microcosm (0.25 g soil) was used to extract DNA using the DNeasy Power Soil Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) according to the manufacturer's protocol. Quantification of extracted DNA was performed using Qubit 2.0 dsDNA HS Assay (Life Technologies Holdings Pte Ltd, Singapore). The extracted DNA was stored at -80 °C until further analysis.

QMEC analysis: DNA extracts were analyzed in technical triplicates using QMEC GeneChip®. Briefly, 3.1 µL of primers, 24.8 µL SYBR Green I Master Mix and 3.1 µL DNA template were added to each well in the QMEC GeneChip®, and then detected by SmartChip PCR system (WaferGen Biosystems, USA) using 16S rRNA gene (F515/R907) as the reference gene. qPCR conditions included an initial denaturation at 95 °C for 10 min, followed by 40 cycles at 95 °C for 30 s, annealing for 30 s at 58 °C and extension for 30 s at 72°C. The melting curve was plotted by WaferGen software

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automatically, and reactions with multiple melting peaks were eliminated. Only amplifications below the threshold cycle (Ct) of 31 were used for downstream analysis.

Gene copy numbers were calculated as follows. (equation 2).

$$\text{Gene copy number} = 10^{(31 - Ct) / (3.33)} \quad (2)$$

All gene copy numbers were subsequently normalized to the 16 s rRNA gene copy number and data was subsequently visualized and analysed in R and R studio using the pheatmap, vegan and ggplot2 R packages.

High-throughput Amplicon sequencing: High-throughput amplicon sequencing of the V3-V4 variable regions of the 16S rRNA gene was performed on a NovaSeq 6000 SP flow cell with PE250 by Novogene Company (China). PCR reactions were conducted with Phusion® High-Fidelity PCR Master Mix (New England Biolabs). Sequence reads from soil microcosms were analyzed with Qiime2 (Bolyen *et al.*, 2019) in accordance with the standard moving pictures tutorial (Caporaso *et al.*, 2011). The GreenGene database was used for taxonomic classification and DADA2 was used to detect Illumina amplicon sequence data, and filter phiX reads. Microbiome data was analyzed and visualized in R and R studio using the microeco and ggplot2 R packages.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Technical validation of QMEC primers using Meta-analysis

CT value analysis: All 71 primer pairs of the QMEC chip exhibited some degree of amplification within the 31 analyzed datasets, however, the number of samples with successful amplification ($0 < CT \leq 31$) varied highly (**Figure 3**). Of the 35 primer pairs targeting C cycling genes, only 18 primer pairs were successfully amplified in more than 50% of analyzed samples, namely the primer pairs targeting the *accA*, *acsA*, *acsE*, *emGDH*, *exg*, *frdA*, *glx*, *gmGDH*, *korA*, *lig*, *manA*, *mct*, *mnp*, *mxoF*, *pccA*, *pmoA*, *rbcL*, and *xylA* genes (**Figure 3A**). The remaining 17 gene targets were detected to a lesser degree, and in particular, the *AmyX*, *cdaR*, *exc* and *IsoP* genes were only detected in very few samples (less than 25 %), suggesting that these genes might be rare or that the primers may be too specific. For the primers targeting sulfur cycling genes, almost all exhibited successful amplification in at least 50% of all samples, the only exception being the *dsrB* encoding a sulfite reductase beta subunit (**Figure 3B**). For the N cycling genes, 10 primer pairs were detected in at least 50 % of all samples, namely *gdh*, *acsA*, *napA*, *narG*, *nifH*, *nirK1*, *nirK3*, *nirS1*, *nirS2*, *nosZ1*, *nosZ2* (**Figure 3C**). The remaining primers were detected in fewer samples, especially the four primers *hzo*, *hzoA*, *nasA*, and *ureC*, suggesting that these genes might be rare or that the primers may be too specific. Only 3 of the primers used for phosphorus cycling genes were detected in more than 50% of all samples, while the remaining 6 were more rarely detected especially the *cphY* gene (**Figure 3D**).

Figure 1. Percentage of detected Ct value in three categories ($0 < Ct < 31$; $Ct > 31$; $Ct = 0$) using 71 function genes associated with C cycles (A), S cycle (B), N cycle (C) and P cycle (D) in QMEC chip system. Ct value is zero means the functional gene cannot be detected in QMEC chip system; Ct value ranging from 0 to 31 means the functional gene can be well amplified and quantified in QMEC chip system; Ct value higher than 31 means the functional gene can be detected, but the relative abundance is too low to use for downstream analysis.

PCR Amplification efficiency: Robust and precise QMEC chip assays are usually correlated with high PCR efficiency (Bustin *et al.*, 2009). In this study, a PCR efficiency between 1.8-2.1 was considered the optimal range, while values lower than 1.8 were considered problematic. The results showed that 39 of the 71 primers (19 primers targeting C cycling genes, 12 primers targeting N cycling genes, 4 primers targeting P cycling genes and 4 primers targeting S cycling genes) exhibited good PCR amplification efficiency with more than 50% of amplifications being in the normal range of 1.8 to 2.1 (**Figure 4**). For the remaining 32 primer pairs, the PCR amplification efficiency was less robust, especially the 9 primer pairs targeting the *AmyX*, *cdar*, *exc*, *IsoP*, *hzo*, *hzaA*, *nasA*, *ureC* and *cphy* genes, which exhibited low efficiency (< 1.8) in more than 75 % of all amplifications, suggesting low robustness and reliability of the PCR amplifications.

Figure 2. The percentage of amplification efficiency in two categories ($1.8 < \text{Efficiency} < 2.1$; $\text{Efficiency} < 1.8$) using 71 function genes associated with C cycle (A), S cycle (B), N cycle (C) and P cycle (D) in QMEC chip system. The efficiency ranging from 1.8 to 2.1 means normal amplification efficiency in QMEC reaction system; the efficiency lower than 1.8 means low amplification efficiency in QMEC reaction system.

Melting curve analysis: Most of the primer pairs showed high proportions (higher than 75%) of amplifications with only one melting peak, indicating that the amplification occurred unproblematic and with only one PCR product in most cases. However, caution should be taken for a few of the primer pairs including the primers targeting the *abfA*, *aclB*, *cdh*, *chiA* and *mmoX* genes involved in the C cycle, the *hzsB*, *nasA*, and *nxA* of the N cycling genes, *phoD* and *ppx* of the P cycling genes, and *dsrB* of the S cycling genes. These primers had a relatively high fraction (more than 30% of reactions) with multiple melting peaks, which could suggest low specificity of the primers or unoptimal assay conditions. For these primer pairs we therefore suggest a more in-depth analysis of the amplicons to investigate their specificity and coverage.

Figure 3. The percentage of detected melting peak in two categories of melting curves (■, One Peak; ■, Multiple Melting Peaks) using 71 function genes associated with C cycles (A), S cycle (B), N cycle (C) and P cycle (D) in QMEC chip system. The proportion were calculated after excluding samples which the primers were not amplified (no peak). Multiple melting peaks means the primer may have no-specific amplification and the results should be cautiously processed; The one melting peak means result is reliable in QMEC thermal cyclers.

In conclusion, based on the meta-analysis, we recommend that the following 18 primer pairs undergo further optimization and validation as they performed suboptimal on one or more of parameters evaluated in the meta analysis: Carbon cycling genes; *AmyX*, *cdaR*, *exc*, *IsoP*, *abfA*, *aclB*, *cdh*, *chiA* and *mnoX*. Nitrogen cycling genes; *hzo*, *hzsA*, *nasA*, *nrxA* and *ureC*. Phosphorus cycling genes; *cphY*, *phoD* and *ppx*. Sulfur cycling genes; *dsrB*.

3.2 Specificity and Coverage of the new ureC primer pair

Amplicon sequencing using the new *ureC* primer pair yielded between 69,763–107,180 high-quality reads across the three tested soil samples. These sequences could be clustered into 2135–2684 OTUs, which were associated with 15 bacterial phyla. The majority of OTUs were affiliated with Proteobacteria accounting for more than 60% of the total ureolytic bacterial community (Figure 4), which corresponds well with previous studies (Sun *et al.*, 2019; Ouyang and Norton, 2020). Other

phyla, including Firmicutes, Planctomycetes, Verrucomicrobia, Bacteroidetes, Cyanobacteria, Deinococcus-Thermus, and Chloroflexi were less abundant and made up less than 40% of the total sequences. The specificity of this primer set was assessed by BLAST searches against the NCBI database and analysis of amplicon sequences. The newly designed primer set targeting the *ureC* gene had a specificity of >70%, suggesting that this primer was applicable in functional gene detection.

Figure 4. Left: Relative abundance of the dominant ureolytic phyla in the soils. The relative abundance is based on the proportions of ureolytic sequences classified at the phylum level. Right: Specificity percentage for the *ureC* gene in the soils. The specificity is based on alignment with the Reference Sequence (RefSeq) database.

3.1 QMEC chip analysis to investigate the impact of glyphosate, Roundup, and Artificial Root exudates on soil functional diversity

The updated QMEC chip successfully quantified and detected between 59-62 functional genes per sample in the microcosm experiment, with limited differences between treatments (i.e. Roundup, glyphosate, and ARE amendment). The overall functional gene composition appeared significantly distinct between soil microcosms receiving ARE and those without (Figure 5), suggesting that the QMEC chip can be successfully employed to study shifts in functional gene composition in soil. The distinguished gene compositions correspond well with an observed change in microbial community composition following ARE addition (Figure 6; PERMANOVA; $R^2=0.22$, $p<0.001$). Almost all detected genes were significantly more abundant in samples receiving ARE compared to samples without ARE. In addition, the new *UreC* gene was detected in relatively high abundance across all samples.

Figure 5. Heatmap showing the relative abundance of functional genes detected by the HT-qPCR QMEC chip array. The color gradient represents the log-transformed relative gene abundance (normalized to the corresponding 16S rRNA gene copy numbers). Each row represent the results of each gene target (i.e. primer set) grouped and color-coded by elemental cycling class. Each column represent a microcosms microbiome sample grouped and color coded according to Artificial root exudate amendment (ARE and Roundup/glyphosate treatment). Columns were clustered based on Euclidean distances.

Figure 6. Principal coordinate analysis (PcoA) of the Operational Taxonomic units (OTUs) composition of the soil bacterial community as affected by artificial root exudates (ARE) and different concentrations of Roundup or glyphosate.

Amendment with Roundup and Glyphosate only had a significant impact in soil microcosms receiving ARE, while no effect was observed in samples without ARE. This corresponded well with our expectation, as bacteria residing in hotspot soils were hypothesized to be more sensitive to the bacteriostatic effect of glyphosate than those living in nutrient-depleted soil as found previously for bacteriostatic antibiotics (Brandt *et al.*, 2009). The impact of the agrochemicals in the ARE amended soil was apparent for N and C cycling genes, where several genes were significantly impacted (Figures 7 and 8). For the N-cycling genes (Figure 7), glyphosate and Roundup significantly increased the abundance of all impacted genes (*HzsB*, *hao*, *nirK*, *amoA* and *nirS*) compared to the untreated control soil.

Figure 7. Boxplot showing the relative abundance (genes per 16s rRNA gene) of functional genes associated with the Nitrogen cycling, which were significantly impacted by glyphosate/Roundup treatments. Boxes in the plot represent the interquartile range between the first and third quartiles (25th and 75th percentiles, respectively), and the horizontal line inside the boxes defines the median. Whiskers show the lowest and highest values within 1.5 times the IQR from the first and third quartiles. P-value indicates significance level of difference between treatments as determined by Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test.

For C-cycling genes (Figure 8), glyphosate and Roundup also had an increasing impact on some of the impacted genes (*acsB*, *amyA*, *acsE*, *exg* and *pmoA*) compared to the untreated control, while the relative abundance of other genes were significantly reduced (*CDH*, *abfA* and *glx*).

Figure 8. Boxplot showing the relative abundance (genes per 16s rRNA gene) of functional genes associated with Carbon cycling, which were significantly impacted by glyphosate/Roundup treatments. Boxes in the plot represent the interquartile range between the first and third quartiles (25th and 75th percentiles, respectively), and the horizontal line inside the boxes defines the median. Whiskers show the lowest and highest values within 1.5 times the IQR from the first and third quartiles. P-value indicates significance level of difference between treatments as determined by Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test.

Overall, the results indicate that the QMEC chip can be successfully used to study changes in soil microbial functional potential following external inputs (e.g. agrochemicals), especially in nutrient-rich soils, and may be useful to assess Work package 5 case studies in the SoildiverAgro consortium.

4 Reference

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5 ANNEXES

Table A1 QMEC GeneChip®: Information of functional genes and their corresponding encoded enzymes. Black genes: C cycle; green genes: N cycle; yellow gene: P cycle; blue genes: S cycle. Detailed primers were listed in previous study- [Zheng et al., 2018](#).

NO.	Gene	Enzyme	NO.	Gene	Enzyme
1	<i>amyA</i>	Alpha amylase	37	<i>hao</i>	Hydroxylamine oxidoreductase
2	<i>amyX</i>	AmyX/pullulanase	38	<i>hzo</i>	Hydrazine oxidase
3	<i>apu</i>	Amylopullulanase	39	<i>hzsA</i>	Hydrazine synthase subunit A
4	<i>lig</i>	Lignin peroxidase	40	<i>hzsB</i>	Hydrazine synthase subunit B
5	<i>mnp</i>	Manganese peroxidase	41	<i>napA</i>	Periplasmic nitrate reductase
6	<i>xylA</i>	Xylose isomerase	42	<i>narG</i>	Nitrate reductase alpha chain
7	<i>accA</i>	AcetylCoA carboxylase carboxyl transferase	43	<i>gdh</i>	Glutamate dehydrogenase
8	<i>aclB</i>	ATP citrate lyase beta-subunit	44	<i>nxrA</i>	Nitrite oxidoreductase
9	<i>cdh</i>	Cellobiose dehydrogenase	45	<i>nasA</i>	Assimilatory nitrate reductase catalytic subunit
10	<i>acsA</i>	Carbon monoxide dehydrogenase	46	<i>amoA1</i>	NH ₄ ⁺ monooxygenase subunit
11	<i>acsB</i>	AcetylCoA synthase	47	<i>amoA2</i>	NH ₄ ⁺ monooxygenase subunit
12	<i>acsE</i>	Methyltetrahydrofolate corrinoid/iron sulfur protein methyltransferase	48	<i>amoB</i>	NH ₄ ⁺ monooxygenase subunit
13	<i>frdA</i>	Fumarate reductase flavoprotein subunit	49	<i>ureC</i>	Urease
14	<i>mct</i>	MesaconylCoA C1C4 CoA transferase	50	<i>nirK1</i>	Nitrite reductase (NO forming)
15	<i>abfA</i>	Arabinofuranosidase	51	<i>nirK2</i>	Nitrite reductase (NO forming)

16	<i>manA</i>	Mannanase	52	<i>niK3</i>	Nitrite reductase (NO forming)
17	<i>mcrA</i>	Methylcoenzyme M reductase alpha subunit	53	<i>nirS1</i>	Nitrite reductase (NO forming)
18	<i>naglu</i>	Nacetylglucosaminidase	54	<i>nirS2</i>	Nitrite reductase (NO forming)
19	<i>pox</i>	Phenol oxidase	55	<i>nirS3</i>	Nitrite reductase (NO forming)
20	<i>chiA</i>	Endochitinase	56	<i>nosZ1</i>	Nitrous oxide reductase
21	<i>rbcL</i>	RubisCO large chain	57	<i>nosZ2</i>	Nitrous oxide reductase
22	<i>pccA</i>	PropionylCoA carboxylase alpha	58	<i>ppx</i>	Exopoly-phosphatase
23	<i>korA</i>	Oxoglutarate ferredoxin oxidoreductase	59	<i>phnK</i>	Phosphonate transport system ATP binding protein
24	<i>cdaR</i>	Carbohydrate diacid regulon	60	<i>phoD</i>	Alkaline phosphatase
25	<i>glx</i>	Glyoxal oxidase	61	<i>phoX</i>	alkaline phosphatase/Pho regulon
26	<i>exc</i>	Exochitinase	62	<i>ppk</i>	ppk3
27	<i>IsoP</i>	Isopullulanase	63	<i>pqqC</i>	Pyrroloquinolinequinone synthase
28	<i>emGDH</i>	Methanol dehydrogenase	64	<i>bpp</i>	Propeller phytase
29	<i>exg</i>	Exoglucanase	65	<i>cphy</i>	Cysteine phytase
30	<i>exoPG</i>	ExoPG	66	<i>gam</i>	Glucoamylase
31	<i>gmGDH</i>	Glucose dehydrogenase	67	<i>soxY</i>	Sulfur oxidation protein
32	<i>smtA</i>	SuccinylCoA:(S) malate CoA transferase	68	<i>apsA</i>	Adenosine phospho-sulfate reductase subunit A
33	<i>mxAF</i>	Methanol dehydrogenase subunit	69	<i>dsrA</i>	Sulfite reductase alpha subunit
34	<i>pmoA</i>	Methane monooxygenase subunit A	70	<i>dsrB</i>	Sulfite reductase beta subunit

35	<i>mmoX</i>	Methane monoxygenase component	71	<i>yedZ</i>	Sulfite oxidase
36	<i>nifH</i>	Nitrogenase iron protein	72		